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D2.2 EAB Report

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GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D2.2

1st Report of the Ethics Advisory Board

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Abstract

Deliverable 2.2 provides the first report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). This report has been compiled after the first meeting of the Ethical Advisory Board held on 19th January 2022.

The meeting was presented with the current position with regards the project objectives and progress, data protection and ethics oversight and assessments for the project.

The EAB Members provided their views on these challenges and added advisory on actions that they agreed they would like to see addressed. These included:

1. Development of a comprehensive mapping of the existing and prospective ethical approvals across the project combined with the data dictionaries, data processing, outputs and activities for each of the partners.
2. Efforts to engage with the project and develop a series of core ethical principles that could underpin and reinforce agreements made between project partners as well as those of with parties, both public and industrial, outside the consortium.
3. Apply the recent European Commission toolkits for assessing risks relating to Artificial Intelligence development and use to address the specific issues GenoMed4All has encountered.

A Chair has been appointed, one of the external experts, who will be supported by i~HD. The next meeting will likely be in six month's time, with a view to holding two meetings a year.

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Ethics, data protection, governance, advisory board, risk management.

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PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

CO Confidential to GENOMED4ALL project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

HDs	Haematological diseases
FL	Federated Learning
NN	Neural Network
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MM	Multiple Myeloma
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
WP	Workpackage
EAB	Ethical Advisory Board
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan

1 Executive summary

Deliverable 2.2 provides the first report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). This report has been compiled after the first meeting of the Ethical Advisory Board held on 19th January 2022.

The meeting was presented with the current position with regards the project objectives and progress, the data protection and ethics oversight and assessments for the project. The EAB Members were provided with key documents relating to the project. These included the ongoing Data Protection Impact Assessment, Data Management Plan, draft consent and patient information leaflets and processes for recording the ethics and other requisite approvals for each of the partners.

The EAB Members were also presented with a preliminary list of ethical challenges that the Workpackage 2 team and their counterparts across other Work packages had to date identified.

The EAB Members provided their views on these challenges and added advisory on actions that they agreed they would like to see addressed. These included:

1. Development of a comprehensive mapping of the existing and prospective ethical approvals across the project combined with the data dictionaries, data processing, outputs and activities for each of the partners.
2. Efforts to engage with the project and develop a series of core ethical principles that could underpin and reinforce agreements made between project partners as well as those of with parties, both public and industrial, outside the consortium.
3. Apply the recent European Commission toolkits for assessing risks relating to Artificial Intelligence development and use to address the specific issues GenoMed4All has encountered.

The EAB Members were broadly satisfied with the approaches taken to date but were keen for materials that described the project in more details than what is currently provided on the project Website. A Chair has been appointed, one of the external experts, who will be supported by i~HD. The next meeting will likely be in six month's time, with a view to holding two meetings a year.

2 Introduction

This Deliverable 2.2 provides the first report of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board (EAB). The EAB has been constituted by inviting three independent experts in the area of advanced techniques for using health data to improve outcomes and foster digital innovation. The EAB goal is to provide an independent view on the ethical robustness of the project and its activities across the consortium partners with specific focus on its protection of data and ethical AI development.

2.1 Role of the EAB

The goal of the EAB is to help to assure that the key elements of ethical consideration, including non-maleficence (for data subjects and project partners), equity, autonomy and an overall consideration of ensuring that the project delivers public good for EU Citizens and beyond, and is not supplanted by other interests. Moreover, the EAB can assure that the regulatory compliance, particularly the with regards the use of data, is in line with reasonable interpretation and solid risk management principles, established by having a keen view of the data protection measures in place.

The EAB must operate independently of the project and remain in a position to review and take a view on its processes, approaches and decisions. It must provide direction on matters that arise and are noted by the project, or those that it identifies as pertinent and requiring attention. To that end, the EAB will meet twice annually, and receive an update form the project. It will receive interim reports from WP2 every three months. In extraordinary circumstances the EAB will review and where appropriate hold extraordinary meetings for any issues that arise affecting the ethical integrity or causing a substantial risk to the regulatory and / or ethical standing of the project.

The EAB's opinion will be final and binding, and the reports that are generated will be made public for both project partners and the wider public alike. The project will liaise with the EAB where their opinions or decisions are not clear.

This report has been compiled after the first meeting of the Ethical Advisory Board held on 19th January 2022. This meeting provided an opportunity for the independent experts to opine on the state of the project with regards ethics and wider risk management. In attendance were three independent Advisory Board Members, the Project Coordinators, and the Work package 2 leads (described in Section 3.1). The meeting preparation required that the EAB Members review a series of compliance artefacts with a preliminary view of the project workpackage partners on particular ethical challenges. This allowed the EAB to take a view on how best to proceed with regards meeting these challenges, and any others that they themselves had identified.

2.2 Structure of this report

This report describes in Section 3 the constitution of the EAB and the processes that were put in place to prepare and conduct the first EAB meeting. The meeting was to that end presented with the current position with regards the data protection and ethics oversight and assessments for the project. The EAB Members were provided with key documents relating to the project. These

included the ongoing Data Protection Impact Assessment, Data Management Plan, draft consent and patient information leaflets and processes for recording the ethics and other requisite approvals for each of the partners.

The report under section 4 describes the key challenges that the project has so far identified, as well as the challenges that the EAB members themselves had uncovered. The EAB Members were presented with a preliminary list of ethical challenges that the Workpackage 2 team and their counterparts across other Work packages had to date identified.

The report under section 5 provides the outcome of the meeting and it concludes with a discussion of the direction provided by the EAB and the next steps to implement the actions that have been provided.

3 Constitution of the EAB and first meeting preparation

The EAB provides the independent advisory oversight of the project as well as wider expertise in the area of ethics, regulatory compliance and risk management for data driven innovation in the health sector. Three external EAB experts are supported by the Project Co-Ordination and Leadership Team, as well as representatives from Work package 2, who provide background and descriptions to the EAB members around the project and provide preparatory materials for the first and subsequent meetings.

3.1 EAB Constitution

The first EAB meeting was held on 19th January 2022 and the Agenda is provided in Annex 1. The constitution described here has been developed to ensure that the EAB had to hand the information and project-specific expertise inputs to provide a fair and impartial overview of the progress and to identify the relevant issues the external experts should deliberate and offer a view of the project's regulatory compliance to date.

The members of the EAB are as follows (in alphabetical order):

- ❑ **Federico Alvarez (UPM, WP1 Lead and Project Coordinator)**
- ❑ **Fracncesco Cremonesi (DW, WP2 member)**
- ❑ **Tommaso Foglia (DW, WP2 Member)**
- ❑ **Nikolaus Forgó (External EAB Member, Professor of IT and IP Law, University of Vienna)**
- ❑ **Annelore Hermann (UPM, WP1 Lead and Project Administration Officer)**
- ❑ **Dipak Kalra (i~HD, WP2 Lead)**
- ❑ **Nathan Lea (i~HD, WP2 Lead)**
- ❑ **Anna Rizzo (DW, WP2 Member)**
- ❑ **Mahsa Shabani (External EAB Member, Assistant Professor in Privacy Law, University of Ghent)**

❑ **Paul Timmers (External EAB Member, Research Associate University of Oxford, Former EU Director European Commission)**

The external EAB experts offer a mixture of skills and backgrounds, from an academic focus on law and ethics around privacy and data protection, through to experience with risk management and process oversight. Through seeking these external members, the project sought to have the relevant competencies to assess the progress of GenoMed4All's ethical and data protection work and its ongoing approach.

The first meeting was facilitated by Dipak Kalra and the agenda included the need to appoint an independent chair. It was agreed that Nikolaus Forgó would be appointed Chair and would receive support from i~HD to prepare meetings in the future. The meeting agreed that the EAB would meet twice a year, or in the event of the need to hold an extraordinary meeting if needed.

3.2 Preparatory Materials

In advance of the EAB the External Members were sent a briefing note and series of documents to orientate them to the project and prepare them for the EAB meeting. These materials were sent out a month in advance of the EAB meeting.

The Deliverables that were shared for the EAB are available via the project archives. The Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) in its current version is available under Annex 2.

The briefing pack provided an overview of the materials for information and represented details that WP 2 identified would likely be of assistance to the EAB to consider the project and prepare its first report.

The Briefing commenced with a brief introduction to the project's objectives and progress, and then a summary of the materials for review. The main ethical considerations that WP2 had identified and proposed for EAB consideration are listed in Section 4.

The briefing note advised the EAB that the project is likely to proceed with retrospective studies for Multiple Myeloma and Myelodysplastic Syndrome, and for Sickle Cell Disease the studies will likely be both retrospective and prospective. For retrospective studies reconciliation with existing ethical approvals and consents was already underway and for prospective studies recruitment processes and criteria and consent forms would of course be required. Both study scenarios were therefore covered in the materials and at the EAB meeting.

The materials provided were as follows:

- ❑ The Data Protection Impact Assessment to date for the consortium wide business for GenoMed4All (provided under Annex 2)
- ❑ The Data Assets Register collected for all sites to date (confirmed and subject to availability on request)
- ❑ Work Package 10 Deliverables, participant inclusion and exclusion criteria, consent procedures, consent forms and information leaflets, provisions for monitoring ethical approval

matters, provisions for monitoring lawful basis selection (as part of the DPIA process) and publication of data dictionaries.

- ❑ A copy of Deliverable 2.1, providing the Data Management Plan and the DPIA.
- ❑ A PowerPoint and PDF describing the partners and their roles and legal responsibilities under GDPR (subject to availability on request).

4 Ethical challenges under consideration

Workpackage 2 identified the following areas that represent its main ethical challenges. These were discussed at the EAB meeting in addition to any particular points that the EAB Members wished to cover.

4.1 Ethical challenges identified by the GenoMed4All

Through working with representatives from across the clinical site teams and university partners who are co-ordinating data flows with not only the preparation of the data management plans and the DPIA, but also the WP10 Deliverables, the following ethical challenges were put to the EAB.

4.1.1 Should GenoMed4All require all data contributing sites to conduct a self-assessment of whether they require any additional Research Ethics Approvals?

This consideration is specific to the considerations around Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence and whether any existing approvals need to be reconsidered as part of the specific ML / AI considerations or whether forthcoming approvals need a specific focus on these matters.

4.1.2 Should GenoMed4All develop its own set of guideline Ethical Principles based on the approvals that the various projects receive?

This would need to be collated and shared with all Work packages within the project where there would thereafter need to be a consensus developed between the partners on such a set of principles. Furthermore, GenoMed4All has a significant interest from parties external to the Consortium. We are therefore looking at how to facilitate their contribution to the data sets and access to the data and machine learning resources. There are data protection and other matters such as IP and liability that need to be considered, but moreover is there a case for ensuring that they are prepared to abide by ethical principles the Consortium develops? The overall question is what the key particulars for Ethical principles should GenoMed4All focus on?

4.1.3 Representativeness of the data sets, particularly around ethnicity and gender

The representativeness of the data sets is particularly challenging since the disease areas focus on rare diseases. There is a risk where GenoMed4All teams who have a focus on developing algorithms will not have a sense of this, especially since they do not have a clinical perspective.

This will need to be addressed by further meetings with clinical contributors and whilst AI methods can offset some of the imbalance (especially around the use of coarsened population data). This raises the question of data exclusion and the risks of perturbing the realistic representation of the data and how it represents the care interventions.

4.1.4 Availability of data based on the representative population numbers.

In the case of SCD, the criteria for inclusion have not been rigid because of the population numbers. This presents a different challenge however because looking at data across patients with a broad set of inclusion criteria may confuse the algorithms, representing a challenge for the machine learning. A possibility is to isolate records that are best for assisting with machine learning, whilst also considering records that would be better used for algorithm validation. Essentially the data is heterogenous and may be confusing for the algorithms but there is still a need to validate the algorithms and the results of the algorithm assessments as well. It is important to ensure an ethical basis upon which to select and use the data for each purpose, but GenoMed4All can take into account these steps for other diseases.

4.2 Other preliminary views

In addition to the ethical challenges GenoMed4All had identified, prior to the meeting EAB members had noted that the project was impressive including a large number of partners and a significant work plan. The initial responses on reviewing the materials prior to the meeting included a request from one EAB Member for materials that could help introduce the project. Prior to the meeting WP2 requested that the EAB Members review the Project Website, which would help indicate to the project whether the Website was helping readers understand GenoMed4All.

5 Outcome of the meeting

5.1 Meeting administration

The meeting agreed that Nikolaus Forgó would chair future meetings with assistance from i~HD for materials gathering, agenda setting and updates on the project, and UPM for arranging the scheduling and meeting facilities (virtual or face to face as appropriate).

The EAB agreed to hold meetings twice each calendar year, and in the event of the need for an extraordinary meeting GenoMed4All would facilitate that.

5.2 Outcome of EAB discussions

The EAB Members were overall satisfied with the progress of the Ethical and Regulatory matters around data handling but recognised the complexity of the project and the challenges that entailed. They enquired as to how the ethical approvals were being managed and whether ethical approvals had been given for the project.

5.2.1 Proposed ethical and regulatory mapping exercise

The response from WP2 was that in some cases for retrospective studies using previously collected data, existing ethical approvals covered this reuse - at the confirmation of the individual sites who were responsible for sharing the data. In some cases sites were in the process of seeking ethics approvals for these retrospective studies, or indeed that they were assessing the need for amendments to existing approvals and / or consents so that data can be shared.

Furthermore, in some cases partners would be conducting prospective studies that would involve the need to approach participants for consent, seek new ethical approvals and / or setup a new study to gather the data needed for the project. These cases would be supported by the requirements deliverables from WP 10, which would serve as a basis for the development of consent forms and information leaflets, and / or application the ethics review boards locally where needed.

The EAB Members were satisfied with this explanation but felt that the project required to adopt a new and formal approach to recording the progress of both the data protection compliance and ethical oversight for retrospective and prospective data use to ensure that partners were supported in what they needed to achieve locally in order to ensure ethical and legal participation in the project. This tallied with the first of the ethical challenges that GenoMed4All had identified, which asked the EAB whether they felt a local site confirmation of ethical approval and self-assessment was necessary. The EAB advised to stay at the safe side, i.e. ask for such self-assessment, at this stage.

To that end the EAB advised the development of a comprehensive mapping of both the ethical and data protection particulars for the project. This mapping would need to include the existing and prospective ethical approvals across the project. This would need to be combined with the learnings from the DPIA and DMP preparations, development of the data processing pipelines and use of the algorithms on the central platforms or at the sites. These details will be combined with the data dictionaries, data processing, outputs and processing activities for each of the partners. This mapping would follow the flow of data for source sites through to the central collection of data for machine learning.

The EAB also appreciated the fact that GenoMed4All has a dual approach for project delivery. The first is for the project to collect the data centrally to train the AI algorithms. The second is to run the algorithms at the data source both for training and advisory. These approaches will be applied across most, if not all, partners and will also form the basis of external party collaboration.

The EAB appreciated the importance of this level of scrutiny and that development of a mapping that includes this detail is essential. The mapping must be based not only on the flows but also a reconciliation with the Data Dictionary, DPIA and update to the DMP.

This would also serve as the basis to assist sites in such a self-assessment of ethical approvals. It would help mitigate challenges around recording of approvals, including in cases where the approvals may be provided in a language other than English and where compliance delays or uncertainties could be addressed.

5.2.2 Development of ethical and legal principles for the project

In addition to the mapping exercise, the EAB supported the proposed development of project-wide ethical principles for the project to assist in not only the awareness and oversight of the partners, but also to align equivalence in terms of ethical standards with parties external to the consortium. The EAB highlighted the importance of the robust mapping exercise that they recommended in supporting this and assisting with the practical implementation of principles.

5.2.3 Managing representation and bias

The issues around data subject and disease severity representation and bias that had been identified by GenoMed4All and have been described in sub-sections 4.1.3 and 4.1.4 are complex matters that need some additional consideration. The EAB Members recommended the use of the recent European Commission toolkits for assessing risks relating to Artificial Intelligence [1] development and use to address the specific issues GenoMed4All has encountered.

The recommendation would help the project and the EAB to identify those risks more explicitly as well as take a view as to whether they can be addressed or need to be accepted and provided as part of the results of the project.

6 Conclusions

The first EAB meeting resulted in a set of important and useful activities to help bolster the ethical and regulatory robustness of GenoMed4All and its approach. The first task as next steps will be to formulate the mapping exercise where the materials gathered to date will provide a firm foundation to move this work forward.

The development of a set of ethical principles will be informed by this activity and will help to integrate the AI risk assessment approach into the existing Data Protection by Design and Default approach that WP2 is currently operating.

In the coming months GenoMed4All partners will need to establish contractual relationships between the partners both internal and external. This could be achieved if there are doubts around the ethical approvals and individual partner situations as they themselves will not be keen to enter into contract without their own assurances. It may be the case that WP2 and the other partners look to isolate cases in point around contractual agreements where the project can advise on whether signatories can achieve the goals that they are trying to achieve, or a more gradual approach is needed.

The EAB will receive an update report within the next three to four months.

¹ <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/best-practices/ai-impact-assessment-code-conduct>

7 Appendix 1 Data Protection Impact Assessment

7.1 Introduction to IG Assessment process

Under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is only required where proposed data processing is “likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons” (Article 35(1)). However, Article 35(3) explicitly requires one where there is ‘large-scale’ processing of ‘special category’ (e.g. healthcare) data then a DPIA is required.

One other possibility is that the data being processed is already anonymised (see Recital 26) so falls outside GDPR altogether so that no DPIA is actually required.

However, good project management and information governance suggests that there should be a general approach to risk assessment for any project or business enterprise – if only to determine whether a DPIA might be required.

Ideally, one should work from a simple initial Checklist (this document) which identifies possible areas of information risk and compliance requirements to a ‘discussion note’ which explores any issues in more depth and may help identify the necessary mitigation methods and mechanisms to offset most if not all risks. Only if risks are unmitigated or remain ‘high’ would you move to a formal DPIA report.

For the purposes of GenoMed4All, this DPIA has been developed as an overarching assessment for use by the individual Consortium Partners to advise them of their own regulatory compliance requirements. This document represents a Consortium view of the overall data handling within the project and whilst it is not a legal entity in and of itself, it is formed of legal entities that may have a data controller (joint or several) or processor role and would therefore need to similarly take a view as to whether they need to run a DPIA as part of their compliance.

Deliverable 2.1 outlines the rationale for this approach, as well as how the DPIA has been developed.

7.2 The IG Assessment approach

There should be an overview of the proposed project or business change to explain what processing is envisaged as well as the purpose and intended outcome. The ‘purpose’ is important to establish the legal basis for the processing as well as ensuring that any possible mitigations or counter-measures do not undermine the main rationale for the processing.

The next step is to establish what compliance requirements may apply: GDPR, contractual or other regulatory restrictions, consent requirements, or obligations to preserve the data for legal or other reasons (including the benefit of posterity perhaps).

Once the precise range of obligations has been established, then appropriate checks can be made and recorded within the document.

The most obvious of these being GDPR compliance. There must be a ‘High Risk’ assessment (Appendix A) to determine whether the supervisory authority needs to be informed – generally, it

is expected that it will not be necessary; if so, then a formal DPIA report will be needed and this remains the responsibility of the

Appendix B has a broader Privacy Impact Assessment that may throw up some broader issues. Initial conclusions as to next steps or particular countermeasures to be considered should be detailed below.

7.3 Project Background/Overview

GenoMed4All seeks to develop an integrated repository of genetic data that will provide learning materials for advanced analytics algorithms and artificial intelligence driven diagnostic tooling. It focuses on three rare disease areas including Sickle Cell Disease (SCD), Multiple Myeloma (MM) and Myelodysplastic Syndrome (MDS). The data required for this includes the genetic information gathered from consented participants, as well as clinical data items

The GenoMed4All Consortium is a pan-European group of institutions that hold clinical, research, technical infrastructure and advanced analytics expertise. A full list of the partners and their roles in the Consortium are currently provided in the Legal and Roles and Liabilities presentation available [here](#) where the details of their responsibilities are defined in detail.

Additional materials relevant to this DPIA are the Assets Register and Project Partner Details available [here](#) and the questionnaires designed to explore and discover further GDPR related requirements are available on request.

7.3.1 Comparison of process steps (simplified): [optional]

This allows identification of what processing is new or changed through the project:

Step	Current	Proposed
This relates to the GenoMed4All Consortium and the associated projects. It is designed to cover a generic assessment for all the projects within the Consortium	There are existing initiatives and those that have yet to start. The disease Areas include Multiple Myeloma (MM), Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS)	Workpackage 2 proposed that we initially focus on the VHIR processing as a start to explore how we apply this DPIA and offer it to sites to complete their own DPIAs as required. We have asked Francesco di Tano to review for MM and Humanitas for MSD.
Val d'Hebron - VHIR Project - SCD	Creation of a database of Sickle Cell Patients with demographic data, clinical data, labs data and a link with a biobank (also storing biological samples from these patients) as well as genetic data.	Reuse and generate new data within the GenoMed4All project. This will provide a basis for the development of AI algorithms for patients' risk stratification.
UNIBO - MM	Preparing to enable data sharing from themselves and other partners (UNIBO has a repository already but does it already include the other partner data providers' data?)	As with SCD, MM is looking to collate and share data for understanding risk stratification and disease management.
HUMANITAS - MDS	As with SCD and MM, but have particular interest in onboarding external partners.	As above (TBC with HUMANITAS)

Step	Current	Proposed
Sharing of Pseudonymised data to a central shared repository of pseudonymised data	These proposals are currently in development and are listed under the Platform Ideation Workshop Summary Slides	There are four options proposed for 5 different use cases. Each involve the sharing of pseudonymised data only (where pseudonymisation would likely use the EUPID tool to add a pseudonym though this is under discussion). The pseudonymised data will be held in a central repository where data will be accessed according to the Data Sharing Agreements that are put in place between provider and recipients.
Retrieval of Pseudonymised Data for local AI research	This is planned for sites to retrieve the pseudonymised data and conduct the AI and ML analyses locally within their repositories	At this point it is unclear whether a Data Sharing Agreement between providers and recipients within the consortium would suffice for 1. Sharing data to the central platform and 2. Onward sharing with local recipient partners. It may be the case that the platform is run by a processor under instruction and the data is thereafter accessed under the terms of a DSA across partners. This could perhaps cover the four disease areas severally.
Sharing of data to Third Countries (including US)	Genome Wide Association Studies' (GWAS) data will need to be shared with US and possibly UK to identify Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNP).	This should be possible where new Standard Contractual Clauses have been published week commencing 14 th June 2021 that cover the Schrems 2 ruling. The issue will be that there may be specific Member State Legislation that provides for particular care of Genetic and GWAS data (where partners will need to confirm this). N.B. where would the SNPs go? Into the Central Repository?

7.4 Initial Conclusions

concerning further counter-measures or business viability [possibly tentative]

1. We are starting to explore the GenoMed4All process by doing a deep review of VHIR's project. This will allow the Consortium to explore the other flows for the other sites so that we can develop an overarching DPIA that will inform the other sites moving forward. There may be requirements for additional IRB approvals and site approvals and this will be assessed by means of a questionnaire that the VHIR DPIA will help us to articulate. Where VHIR is mentioned it will be the case that this is applicable to MM and MDS disease areas.
2. There will need to be clarification on the points where DSAs will need to be applied and their scope. i~HD can provide core templates for data classes and their sharing and use requirements as well as some core particulars that would go into a DSA but these will need to be populated and executed as contracts by local partner teams.
3. The Consortium Agreement makes clear that all partners will act as separate and distinct controllers. There may be the need to allow the partners responsible for hosting the central platform to act as processors under instruction. However are the partners not joint controllers over the central platform?

Fig1. DFD General Draft

7.4.1 Compliance Checks required:

Tick	Requirement	Notes [replace guide text with response]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Does the project involve processing 'personal data' of any sort?	Note: not just patient data; may need clear assessment of any anonymization to establish outside GDPR/. Yes – source data held by VHIR in its existing repositories will need to be processed under its existing approvals; Additionally, there will be some clinical record processing to capture data within the health record. Further, there will be handling of existing Genetic Data that had been derived from Samples, and there will likely be additional processing of biological samples to generate genomics and metabolomics data, including Genome Wide Association Studies' (GWAS) data for Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNP) identification. In conclusion there will be processing of existing and generation of new data. Samples are in the Biobank and these samples will be processed for the omics data.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Does the project involve processing 'confidential data' of any sort?	Note: may be 'commercial in confidence', medical confidentiality, or organisational confidentiality (internally sensitive); may need to check contractual limitations. Yes – this will include medical records, research profiles, existing omics data from existing registries, generation of new omics data. Participants will not however be approached or involved.
Data Availability requirements		

Tick	Requirement	Notes [replace guide text with response]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Does data need to be held for GCP compliance?	Possible – there is a possibility of developing a medical device in the future but in the scope of GenoMed4All the algorithms will be developed and validated but it will not be tested as part of a live participant trial. The goal of GenoMed4All in this case is to develop a validated model as a preparation for clinical trials and medical device development in the future. There is no risk to the participants or their care management within the scope of GenoMed4All.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Does data need to be held to meet 'Open Data' requirements?	FAIR Principles will be followed and Open Access publications will be provided. Data sets themselves may be made available where this needs to be discussed and decided by the project. Refer to D2.1 for the Data Management Plan
<input type="checkbox"/>	Does data need to be held to meet ICMJE requirements or commitments?	Yes. Projects will be signed up to Clinical Trials(.gov) and the EU equivalents.

7.4.2 GDPR Compliance Checklist – where ‘personal data’ is processed:

Tick	Requirement	Notes [replace guide text with response]
Article 5: Principles compliance checks		
<input type="checkbox"/>	a) Is processing lawful, fair, and transparent?	The processing must be pursuant to a favourable ethical opinion and work within the bounds of approvals that have already been granted. Additionally, where amendments may be required, this will be checked by means of the questionnaires that will be provided to sites so that we can reconcile the existing approvals and the proposed processing (e.g. additional samples processing for generating genomics and metabolomics sequences). Transparency will be assured by checking existing PILs and/or ICFs and developing further transparency and awareness materials.
<input type="checkbox"/>	b) Is the purpose (or purposes) of the processing clearly defined	['purpose limitation' so should cover any subsequent or later processing] Yes – this is for scientific research in the public interest and specifically the development of AI algorithms and their validation for risk stratification.
<input type="checkbox"/>	c) adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary	['data minimisation'] TBC – this will include the parameters and the methodology to determine the parameters that required as assessed by the scientific team. (Please see annexes).
<input type="checkbox"/>	d) accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date	TBC – this will depend on the existing flows and processes and any SOPs COPs for data capture and curation. This will also include semantics and codification of data. How is mapping done and validated?
<input type="checkbox"/>	e) kept and permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary	['storage limitation'] TBC – the retention of data will be in line with Article 89 requirements, specific to each step in the data processing needs and made available as per the requirements for data retention (likely Spanish jurisdiction – possibly up to 25 years).

Tick	Requirement	Notes [replace guide text with response]
<input type="checkbox"/>	f) processed securely	TBC – needs data flow diagram to be completed. The first phase will be the development of the algorithms and they will need to share pseudonymised data in a central repository (we will need to be clear which European country the data will be held) where DXE in France will be responsible for this; the second phase will involve validation that will require a more federated approach. There is a generic DFD above that describes the general flows across 4 options for deployment and 5 Use Cases.
<input type="checkbox"/>	2) can you demonstrate this compliance?	['accountability'] TBC. We will need to specify a set of questions for each site.
Articles 13 & 14 compliance		[See detailed Transparency Checklist below]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Did the data come from publicly accessible sources?	[if so then transparency requirements may be reduced, but need to ensure data is accurate & up-to-date] No
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are data subjects informed before processing starts for any new purpose if incompatible with original purpose where the controller wants to use data for a different purpose to the purpose for which they currently hold data	Check protocol for additional processing.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Does the Privacy Notice and/or PIL cover this processing?	Is there a PIL / Notice? These can be found ICF. There has been one drafted as part of the SCD general protocol for sites.
<input type="checkbox"/>	What patient choices are available? Are these explained?	[see also Data Subject Rights below] What choice is offered? These are clear in the Consent Forms for the SCD general protocol and ICF.
Articles 6 and 9: legal bases		
<input type="checkbox"/>	What are legal bases under Article 6	Likely Public Task or Consent (to be confirmed by sites)
<input type="checkbox"/>	What are legal bases under Article 9 (if 'special category' data)	Likely J – Scientific Research in the Public Interest.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are Article 6 legitimate interests explained where relevant?	[Complete an LIA form]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are details of statutory obligations for Article 6 explained where relevant.	[Quote statutes or regulation]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Is this proposed processing compatible with the declared purposes?	[Check against any privacy notices and public information]
Article 89(1) research exemption		

Tick	Requirement	Notes [replace guide text with response]
<input type="checkbox"/>	If for research, do we meet Art 89(1) data minimisation	Yes
Articles 15-23: Data Subject Rights		[See detailed table below]
<input type="checkbox"/>	Do we support data subject rights?	[If data is pseudo-/anonymised, then it would be difficult/impossible to do so]
<input type="checkbox"/>	There is no use of automated decision making (e.g. profiling)	[Otherwise need at least a 'discussion note'] The project involves machine learning which is a form of profiling. This will be used for Decision Support Services under Use Case 4.
Articles 24-43: Controller-Processor		
<input type="checkbox"/>	A28 & 29: What measures are there to ensure processors comply?	[Is there a formal Data Processing Agreement] A DPA / DSA will be required for data transfers to the central platform and access controls, as well as onward sharing with Consortium Partners. This will be based on data sharing and processing agreement templates that are conformant with requirements provided by i~HD, which will need to be established across partners locally. There remains some uncertainty over whether platform management partners are processors. CINECA is clearly a processor but DEDALUS may be a controller.
<input type="checkbox"/>	A30: Is there an entry for this processing/data held in the register?	GenoMed4All will need to keep a register and local sites should do the same. This can be the same as the Data Sharing and Processing Template that will form part of the DSA Template.
<input type="checkbox"/>	A32-34: Do we ensure appropriate security, including protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage, using appropriate technical or organisational measures?	[separate security checklist?] This is a matter for each partner to attend to and by virtue of this DPIA sites can conduct their own assessments locally to offer appropriate assurance.
<input type="checkbox"/>	A37-39: Is there a DPO and have they been or will they be consulted?	[part of sign-off of the DPIA] All partner DPOs will have been consulted but the project needs ongoing review and consideration from all partners. Specific enquiry has been made to the DEDALUS DPO about the controller or processor role.
Articles 44-50: International transfers		

Tick	Requirement	Notes [replace guide text with response]
	What form of data will be transferred to a third country or international organisation	[describe nature of data and whether identified, identifiable, de-identified or anonymous] GWAS data (which may be regarded as personal and special category)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are there safeguards for international transfers?	[e.g. US Privacy Shield, anonymisation, GDPR equivalence, approved contractual clauses, or BCR] The US is the likely recipient of GWAS data and likely the new SCCs from the EC will be used (published week commencing 14th June 2021). These SCCs have now been published as at December 2021 and a new treaty between EU and US for data transfers is expected in Q1 2022.
Article 90: Obligations of secrecy		
<input type="checkbox"/>	Do we meet medical confidentiality requirements?	[Note any national case law and statutory requirements that may affect this] There may be specific secondary legislation around use of genetic data.

7.4.3 Data Subject Rights:

Note if supported and what process/procedure applies; if not, then describe the legal justification for not supporting this right.

<input type="checkbox"/>	To be informed: about processing, about choices, about rights, about controller	This will form part of a GenoMed4All privacy notice and will be added to the Informed Consent Forms. Individual Sites will need to specify the controllers from the study perspective. Likely the consents sought for GenoMed4All will be in addition to existing studies.
<input type="checkbox"/>	the right of access to see or receive a printed copy	Data is pseudonymised within GenoMed4All and is likely going to be linked anonymised so it may not be applicable for individuals to receive copies of their data. This could be satisfied at source.
<input type="checkbox"/>	the right to rectification – to correct any material errors in the personal data	As above – data will need to be corrected at source
<input type="checkbox"/>	the right to erasure – where appropriate, to ask that all personal data is erased	This will need to be addressed at source in line with research governance retention requirements

		should a participant withdraw from a study.
<input type="checkbox"/>	the right to restrict processing – to ask that some or all processing ceases [see opt-out]	As for Erasure.
<input type="checkbox"/>	the right to data portability – this only applies to data provided directly by individual	To be handled at source.
<input type="checkbox"/>	the right to object to and not to be subject to automated decision-making, including profiling	To be handled at source.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Right to object to a Data Processing Authority (typically the relevant supervisory authority of each Member State)	To be handled at source.
<input type="checkbox"/>	Where consent is the legal basis, the right to withdraw consent	To be handled at source.

7.5 Detailed Transparency Checklist²

Does privacy information provided to data subjects include:

<input type="checkbox"/>	The name and contact details of our organisation	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The name and contact details of our representative (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The contact details of our data protection officer (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The purposes of the processing	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The lawful bases for the processing	[Art6 for 'personal data' & Art9 for 'special category']
<input type="checkbox"/>	The legitimate interests for the processing (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The categories of personal data obtained (if the personal data is not obtained from the individual it relates to)	[for Art14]
<input type="checkbox"/>	The recipients or categories of recipients of the personal data	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The details of transfers of the personal data to any third countries or international organisations (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The retention periods for the personal data.	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The rights available to individuals in respect of the processing	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The right to withdraw consent (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The source of the personal data (if the personal data is not obtained from the individual it relates to)	[For Art14]
<input type="checkbox"/>	The details of whether individuals are under a statutory or contractual obligation to provide the personal data (if applicable, and if the personal data is collected from the individual it relates to)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	The details of the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling (if applicable)	
<input type="checkbox"/>	We provide individuals with privacy information at the time we collect their personal data from them – or where we obtain personal data from a source other than the individual it relates to, we provide them with privacy information	

² Taken from UK Information Commissioner's Office template as an example

<input type="checkbox"/>	within a reasonable of period of obtaining the personal data and no later than one month	
<input type="checkbox"/>	if we plan to communicate with the individual, at the latest, when the first communication takes place	
<input type="checkbox"/>	if we plan to disclose the data to someone else, at the latest, when the data is disclosed	
<input type="checkbox"/>	We provide the information in a way that is: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> concise; <input type="checkbox"/> transparent; <input type="checkbox"/> intelligible; <input type="checkbox"/> easily accessible; and <input type="checkbox"/> uses clear and plain language. 	[Describe how we check is Plain English, etc.]
<input type="checkbox"/>	When drafting the information, we: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> undertake an information audit to find out what personal data we hold and what we do with it. <input type="checkbox"/> put ourselves in the position of the people we're collecting information about. <input type="checkbox"/> carry out user testing to evaluate how effective our privacy information is 	[Note: best practice advice]
<input type="checkbox"/>	When providing our privacy information to individuals, we use a combination of appropriate techniques, such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> a layered approach; <input type="checkbox"/> dashboards; <input type="checkbox"/> just-in-time notices; <input type="checkbox"/> icons; and <input type="checkbox"/> mobile and smart device functionalities. 	[Note: best practice advice]

7.5.1 Security & Access Control Checklist

Controls need to be appropriate to level of risk: identified special category data needs more protection against potential misuse than non-personal data.

	Data Security classification (above Official)	<input type="checkbox"/> - Official-Sensitive <input type="checkbox"/> - Secret <input type="checkbox"/> - Top Secret <input type="checkbox"/> - Public Domain
<input type="checkbox"/>	Personal Data involved [GDPR]	Yes (though within GenoMed4All Pseudonymised)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Special Category of personal data involved [GDPR]	Yes – health and genetic data (though pseudonymised / anonymous)
<input type="checkbox"/>	Electronic Communications (inc. cookies) [PECR]	Yes – website access
<input type="checkbox"/>	Credit Card data	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Legal enforcement [LED2018]	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Financial data	N/A
<input type="checkbox"/>	Intellectual Property (detail owner)	Yes – sites likely retain existing IP and have rights to arising IP
<input type="checkbox"/>	Commercial in confidence (detail owner)	TBC
	Data Location (storage or processing) (include any back-up site(s))	<input type="checkbox"/> - UK <input type="checkbox"/> - EU/EEA x <input type="checkbox"/> - EU White-list x <input type="checkbox"/> - USA x <input type="checkbox"/> - Other:
<input type="checkbox"/>	Is data held in secure data centre?	[detail centre and what certification supports assertion] TBC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Is this new supplier, location, or system?	[If so, need specific IS check; also need formal contract] TBC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Is all user access subject to 2-factor authentication?	<input type="checkbox"/> - no control <input type="checkbox"/> - single factor (e.g. just password) <input type="checkbox"/> - 2-factor (e.g. password & fob) <input type="checkbox"/> - biometric [note: GDPR reqs] <input type="checkbox"/> - Other control:
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are there established JML procedures?	[Joiners, Movers, Leavers] TBC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are there checks that passwords are robust and secure enough?	TBC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are all administrator & user accounts routinely monitored?	[Particularly for redundant or little used accounts] TBC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are systems protected against malware and other attacks?	[provide details of protection software and procedures] TBC

[Need some aspect of CIA/impact-likelihood assessment]

7.5.2 Information Asset Register Checklist

<input type="checkbox"/>	Are there new IAs being created?	[provide details] Yes – Central Platform
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<input type="checkbox"/>	Are old IAs being retired?	[provide details] No
<input type="checkbox"/>	Have IAOs & IACs been consulted?	TBC – for sources
<input type="checkbox"/>	Has IAR been updated/amended?	[at least create project task to do so] GenoMed4All will create its own but sources must also
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data Retention classification & period	TBC
<input type="checkbox"/>	Data retention procedure/functionality in place	TBC

7.5.3 Appendix A – Supervisory Authority ‘High Risk’ Check

If the DPIA shows ‘high risk’ processing which cannot be mitigated, then the DPIA should be sent to the relevant authority for review before any processing starts. Note that their review may take several weeks to process. A ‘High Risk’ assessment represents a ‘risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals’ – so may extend beyond GDPR consideration, including Human Rights.

GDPR Article 35(3) provides three examples:

- a) a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person;
- b) processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 1013; or
- c) a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale

As a case in point the UK ICO cites the following but a different Supervisory Authority definition can be provided if needed:

1. Systematic and extensive profiling with significant effects
2. Large scale use of sensitive data [viz. ‘special category’ in GDPR terms]
3. Public monitoring

These being the same as (a)-(c) above. They further identify the following, where this template can periodically be reconciled with appropriate Supervisory Authority for each Member State’s guidance as appropriate :

1. **New technologies:** processing involving the use of new technologies, or the novel application of existing technologies (including AI).
2. **Denial of service:** Decisions about an individual’s access to a product, service, opportunity or benefit which is based to any extent on automated decision-making (including profiling) or involves the processing of special category data.
3. **Large-scale profiling:** any profiling of individuals on a large scale.
4. **Biometrics:** any processing of biometric data.
5. **Genetic data:** any processing of genetic data, other than that processed by an individual GP or health professional for the provision of health care direct to the data subject.
6. **Data matching:** combining, comparing or matching personal data obtained from multiple sources.
7. **Invisible processing:** processing of personal data that has not been obtained direct from the data subject in circumstances where the controller considers that compliance with Article 14 would prove impossible or involve disproportionate effort.
8. **Tracking:** processing which involves tracking an individual’s geolocation or behaviour, including but not limited to the online environment.
9. **Targeting of children or other vulnerable individuals:** The use of the personal data of children or other vulnerable individuals for marketing purposes, profiling or other automated decision-making, or if you intend to offer online services directly to children.
10. **Risk of physical harm:** Where the processing is of such a nature that a personal data breach could jeopardise the [physical] health or safety of individuals.

‘High Risk’ assessment using ICO criteria:

Criterion:	Assessment	Comments
New technologies	Low	AI and ML
Denial of service	No	
Large-scale profiling	No	
Biometrics	No	
Genetic data	High	
Data matching	TBC	
Invisible processing	No	
Tracking	No	
Targeting of children or other vulnerable individuals	Medium	
Risk of physical harm	If blood samples are collected	

[The assessment can be one of N/A (not applicable), Low, Medium, or High. The comments should explain how the assessment is justified.]

7.6 Appendix B – Broad Privacy Risk Assessment:

#	Risk Description/detail	Discussion
1.	Data accuracy and timeliness	[Is data accurately recorded & kept up-to-date?]
2.	Differential treatment of patients/data subjects	[Might certain categories of people be adversely affected, e.g. children, vulnerable adults]
3.	Data Accuracy and identification	[Is the identification of individual reliable? Is there a danger of mis-attribution or incorrect linkage of data?]
4.	Holding / sharing / use of excessive data within [Company] systems	[Might too much data be held or for long? Is there a clear justification for data retention? Not 'just in case']
5.	Data held too long within [Company] systems	[Is there a clear data retention period specified and are there processes to ensure its deletion when no longer needed? Are copies tracked and deleted as well?]
6.	Excessive range of access in terms of users to personal data (consider new users/change of access privileges)	[Do more users have access than strictly necessary? Are user roles clear distinguished and reflected in the access privileges? Is there a clear process for granting and revoking access privileges?]
7.	Potential for misuse of data, unauthorised access to systems	[What are the likely threats to the data? What countermeasures are or might be applied? Is it possible for access to be granted inappropriately?]
8.	New sharing of data with other organisations, including new or change of suppliers	[Is data being shared from new data providers or with new data users? Are there new suppliers or data processors? What controls will apply?]
9.	Variable and inconsistent adoption / implementation	[How well will this system work end-to-end? How robust is it against partial adoption or system failure?]
10.	Legal compliance, particularly DP transparency requirements and support for data subject rights	[How well does this system meet legal requirements – or appear to meet legal requirements? Does it meet the 'No surprises' rule? What would happen if an individual requests data erasure or ceasing processing, etc.]

#	Risk Description/detail	Discussion
11.	Medical confidentiality	[Are there any addition sensitivities over confidentiality? Might specific approval (e.g. REC) be required to support this processing?]

